

THE LINGUOCULTURAL PECULIARITIES OF ANTHROPONYMS IN THE PHRASEOLOGICAL LAYER OF ENGLISH AND UZBEK LANGUAGES

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ABSTRACT

A phraseological unit is a linguistic unit consisting of two or more word components which represents a single meaning with a particular partial or full figurative meaning, such as to drop a clanger, Peter Pan, as cool as a cucumber. Nowadays, the linguocultural peculiarities of phraseological units with a particular component have been one of debatable and discursive topics in linguistics. In this article, the participation of personal names in the component parts of phraseological units as the representation of culture with several source origins has been discussed.

Key words: anthroponomical phraseology, linguistic system, anthroponym, origin of anthroponyms, cultural peculiarity, etymology of phraseological units

The term “anthroponym” comes from the Greek language, signifying “anthropos” – man, “onyma” – name, and anthroponomics is a branch of onomastics which studies personal names, their distribution, origin, the practical usage of them in society, as well as the systematic structure and development of anthroponyms. Types of proper names, pseudonyms, nicknames and various ways of naming a person can be regarded as the investigative object of anthroponomics.

In modern linguistics under the term “anthroponym” is understood any proper names given to a person or a group of people, such as personal name, patronym, surname, nickname, pseudonym and cryptonym [Sharei, Yazdanmehr & Esfahani, 2017]. The choice of this or that type of anthroponyms is dependent on several circumstances that include the national- cultural values of the people, their age, their residence, their intellectual potential, their aesthetic education, their social position and common views [Jurayeva, 2021]. Anthroponyms, especially personal names, are distinctive from any proper names given to objects and phenomena, that is onyms, with their peculiarity of individualization of the object and every object of nomination include personal names that have special formulae in developed society [Encyclopaedic dictionary of Linguistics, 2008]. Therefore, while the most comprehensively studied types of anthroponyms are

regarded as personal names and surnames, patronyms, nicknames and pseudonyms constitute the types of proper names that entail the anthroponomical system.

Zaytseva, who conducted a research on the stylistic peculiarities of English anthroponyms, accentuates the meanings, origin and peculiarities of English anthroponyms introducing the following factors: 1) a certain group of English personal names date back to the ancient German tribes and such names embodied the symbol of beauty, then they served as a basis to create other names, for example: berth – bright (Berth, Bertold), ed – wealth (Edgar, Edward); 2) a certain group of personal names embodied animals, for example: Anglo- Saxon origin Hengeast (bear) and Scandinavian origin Hari (hare, rabbit); 3) Gaelic, one of the Celtic tribes, people who played an important role in the history and culture of the UK had two- component personal names, for example: Foolchadh (fool – wolf, chadh – warrior); 4) Roman legions brought Latin names onto the British island, such as Arthur, Artorius; 5) a group of German-origin names had two meanings, for example Elstan (gentleman + stone), whereas other group of German- origin names had only one meaning as the representation of appellative process, for example Fisc (fish); 6) a certain group of English names appeared as a result of parental names, which intended to proceed the tradition of that family, for example the king of Kent Eormehr gave such names as Eormenbeorth, Eormenburth and Eormengy to his sons; 7) a certain group of names had Scandinavian origin, such as Asgeirz (Scandinavian origin) > Esgar (British name); 8) as a result of the introduction of Christianity into the British islands, the names related to religious associations appeared, for example, Christmas, Nowell, Easter, Abraham, Adam; 9) a certain group of English names originated from English literature, such as Julia, Juliet, Hermia, Rovenia, Cedric; 10) a certain group of English names had a foreign taste, such as Richard, Yerard, Hugo, William, Nichola [Zaytseva, 1989].

Therefore, while the native layer of English names have their origin of Celts and Anglo- Saxons, who played an important role in the formation of the British culture, the borrowed layer of English names is composed of the Roman, Norman, French, Scandinavian and other origins. Moreover, Christianity and its sacred book Bible, as well as the representatives of English literature contributed to the formation of English names.

The formation of Uzbek names was connected with the primitive period, in which the names represented the concepts of bravery, heroism, agility and the imagination of different divine forces, such as Oyarig', Kuchbars, Alp, Er,

Tangriberdi [Kilichev, 2023]. In the later period, as the result of the introduction, expansion and education of Islam in our territory, Arabic names were introduced into Uzbek people, which meant that Islamic culture had an immense influence on the formation of Uzbek names.

With reference to the origin, meanings and peculiarities of Uzbek names, the following factors can be taken into consideration: 1) associations with religious concepts (Xudoyberdi, Tangriberdi, Xudoyor); 2) the totemistic and animistic beliefs which were practised in names (Bo'riboy, Bo'ritosh, Itolmas); 3) views related to trust in the magical force of names (Ortiqboy, Oltiboy, Xolniso); 4) the zooanthroponomical and fitoanthroponomical component in names (Qo'ziboy, Sarkaboy, Qo'chqor); 5) the ethnographic basis in names to protect the baby from any illnesses and untimely death (To'xta, O'lmas, Toshtemir). Besides, a certain group of Uzbek names is related to historical names and mythological heroes (Hubbi, Qayumar, Jamshid, Kaykovus, Rustam), as well as various ceremonies and customs formed under the influence of Islamic religion (Navro'z, Hayitboy, Ro'ziboy) [Begmatov, 2013].

Therefore, Uzbek names can be divided into native and borrowed layers, the former being those formed with the creation of native people and the latter being the Arabic and Persian origin. Especially, the Islamic culture influenced on the formation of Uzbek names and they developed in harmony with Uzbek literature and culture.

The phraseological units which include anthroponyms as a component have a prominent importance in the linguistic wealth of English and Uzbek people, since anthroponyms have a direct connection with the history, culture, religion, psychology and tradition of those people and applied in the phraseological layer of those languages. Anthroponyms are easily recognised by the language user as the manifestation of exact realias peculiar to a certain nation, being used in one of the components of phraseological units, on the grounds that the linguistic markers laid on the surface of them can be defined without any difficulties.

The personal names used in the anthroponomical component of phraseological units can be regarded to have a direct connection with such sources as historical events and historical people (Cocker, Crichton, Freddy), religious statements (Adam, Judas, David), literary works (Jekyll, Sherlock, Cornelia), mythological characters (Achilles, Cupid, Pandora), national folklore (Tom, Bunch, Fortunatus), political figures (Caesar, Gladstone, Teddy) and common people (Jack, Betty, Charlie).

Certain historical events happened in the past and historical figures who put a remarkable mark in history with their activity or peculiarity made so profound a trace in the social life of English people that they influenced the phraseological layer of English language [Khudoyorova, 2019]. For instance, the phraseological unit “the admirable Crichton”, which is used to describe a person excelling in all kinds of studies and pursuits or being noted for his supreme competence, originated from the name of a Scotch noble James Crichton who was famous for his intellectual and physical prowess.

Bible, the holy book of Christianity, and the characters depicted in that book had a notable impact on the formation of anthroponomical component phraseological units with religious association in English. The book Bible had widely been read by bibliophiles in England for centuries, as a result, the phraseological units, along with individual words, in that book became the integral part of the phraseological layer of the English language [Smith, 1959]. For instance, the phraseological unit “Judas kiss”, which is used to describe an act of betrayal, especially one disguised as a gesture of friendship, emanated from the character Judas, one of the disciples of Jesus the prophet described in Bible, who betrayed Jesus to submit him to authority in return for thirty silver coins.

The characters depicted in the profound literary works by many authors in the wealth of English literature influenced the phraseological layer of the language with their peculiar traits and discernible conducts that those characters' names have become componential part of the phraseological units. For instance, the phraseological unit “Jekyll and Hyde” is used to express a personality which has a pleasant and a very unpleasant side to the character, since this phrase originates from a character called Jekyll, described in the novel “The Strange Case of Dr. Jekyll and Mr. Hyde” by Robert Louis Stevenson, who develops a type of serum that he believes will effectively compartmentalize his dark personality called Hyde when evil urges inside of him. This process happens more regularly until Jekyll becomes unable to control when the transformations occur.

The names of characters mentioned in ancient Greek and Roman myths are also found in the components of phraseological units, which designates that ancient Greek and Roman culture influenced the British culture along with other European countries. For example, the phraseological unit “Pandora’s box”, which is used to describe a process that once begun generates many complicated problems, comes from a character called Pandora depicted in Greek mythology. According to the legend, she out of curiosity opened a box that contained all the evils of the world.

There are also a myriad of names of political figures, military guides, artists as well as writers found in the phraseological units of the English language. For instance, the phraseological unit “appeal to Caesar” signifies addressing to high authority. Its etymological origin dates back to the claim made by the apostle Paul to have his case heard in Rome, which was his right as a Roman citizen.

As the origin sources of personal names which directly influenced the formation of anthroponomical component phraseological units in the Uzbek language, the following factors can be taken into consideration, such as historical events and historical people (Aflotun, Suqrot, Chingizxon), the prophets described in religion (Iso, Muso, Muhammad), literary works and its characters (Majnun, Layli, Nadirmat), national folklore and legends (Rustam, Xizr, Xo’ja Nasriddin) as well as common national people (Eshmat, Ali, Fozil).

The historical figures associated with any historical events, wars and rebellions left so remarkable a trace in the history of Uzbek people that those historical names have possessed the phraseological layer of the Uzbek language. For instance, the phraseological unit “Bo’ji keldi, bo’ji keldi, Chingiz bilan Jo’ji keldi” is associated with the periods when the Mongolian invaders brutally oppressed, unjustly bled, relentlessly menaced and mercilessly plundered the people. Proceeding from this, the phrase is used to intimidate a child if he is not obeying their parents, to halt him from weeping [Shomaqsudov & Shorahmedov, 2018].

Uzbek anthroponomical component phraseological units pertaining to religious statements are particularly connected with the names of prophets, in which case Uzbek culture stands in close relationship with English culture from the viewpoint of the availability of such names in both languages. For instance, the phraseological unit “Iso ham o’z yo’liga, Muso ham o’z yo’liga” is associated with the fact that both Iso (Jesus) and Muso (Moses) were different from each other possessing their own way of guidance and outlook. Proceeding this, the phrase is used to express that everyone will have their own way of life.

The characters and a group of words related with them described in the wealth of Uzbek literary works have become set expressions in an elapse of time, which have a significant role in enriching the phraseological layer of the Uzbek language. For instance, the phraseological unit “Laylini ko’rish uchun Majnuning ko’zlari kerak”, which denotes that beauty lies in lover’s eyes, comes from the characters Layli and Majnun, who were exalted as the representatives of deep perfection of love narrated in a famous Turkish and Persian quintuple “Khamsa”.

Uzbek folklore is abundant in expressive- descriptive means that are discernible in symbolical characters in people's songs, constant epithets, traditional samples, the plenteousness and boundlessness of set expressions, the abundance of caressing and diminutive affixes, in the active and unique use of parallelism and exaggeration. Moreover, such various genres as epic, fairy- tale, proverb, song, riddle, myth, legend and word play were formed to represent events in Uzbek folklore [Safarov, 2010]. The characters' names represented in Uzbek folklore have also intruded the phraseological layer of the language, which metaphorically alludes to their unrepeatable dispositions. For instance, the phraseological unit "Rustami doston bo'lmoq" originates from an epic called "Rustamxon", in which the character Rustam was famous for his athleticism, bravery and being protector of justice. Proceeding this, the phrase is used to say that a person is to be talked by many people for a long time for a prominent trait.

Taking everything into consideration, the linguocultural peculiarities of the history of people and the historical events happened in the past, religion, literature, people's myths and legends, folklore and the characters and heroes reflected in them, which are all regarded to constitute the significant elements of English and Uzbek culture, not only manifest the difference between English and Uzbek nations, but also connect these two nations from viewpoint of common facets. Besides, they notably impact on the formation and appearance of anthroponomical component phraseological units in English and Uzbek languages.

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